

Microbiome research mapping in Horizon 2020: lessons learnt and ways forward for sustainable food systems

Microbiomes are a key component of achieving sustainable food systems. To fully unlock their potential, it is essential that microbiomes are studied across different stages of the food supply chain and in all ecosystems that form part of the food system. This brief lays out key findings of a mapping exercise of Horizon2020 projects around the topic of microbiomes (funded between 2014 and 2022) and provides recommendations on future funding and research needs.

Key outcomes of the mapping:

- 794 projects had *some* microbiome component
- 12 out of 794 projects took a food system approach*
- The funding scale for microbiome projects has remained consistently small throughout Horizon 2020
- The 12 research projects that took a food system approach* had high funding levels of over 5 million Euros
- Projects with a food system approach* covered more research areas than those projects that did not use a systems approach but still did not cover all areas along the food system (e.g. waste streams and food distribution)

Recommendations:

- Closing research gaps and upscaling the funding levels with transdisciplinary projects across both supply chain stages and ecosystems can ensure microbiomes contribute to sustainable and healthy food systems.

* Food system approach was defined as projects that encompass different food supply chain stages or ecosystems within the food system as defined by Microbiome Support

Funding for projects with microbiome component

Research target areas of Microbiome Projects in Horizon 2020

